

30 1.0 INTRODUCTION

31 In the past few decades materials such as ceramic, zeolite and other nanoporous materials
32 including graphene and graphene oxide (GO), have been proposed as potential replacement of
33 existing polymeric membranes for desalination and water purification processes. Among those
34 materials, GO has been studied extensively as, due to its two dimensional (2D) ultrathin
35 structure and controllable surface chemistry[1–3], it can be used as a building block for multi-
36 layered laminated structures (GO membranes) which can be employed in advanced purification
37 and separation processes[4] including desalination of water.[5–8] Recent findings suggest that,
38 not only GO membranes have high selectivity towards mono and divalent metallic ions (those
39 relevant for desalination), [9–12] but also that the water flux in GO membranes is as much as
40 50 LMH/bar,[13] higher than that measured in conventional reverse osmosis membranes (~15
41 LMH/bar).[14,15] The high selectivity is attributed to the possibility to design membranes with
42 very small interlayer spacing (d) (i.e. the average distance between the GO flakes) up to around
43 0.7 nm, which defines the nanopore size. [16–18] GO membranes are hydrophilic materials
44 that can adsorb water even in a low humidity environment.[19,20] This hydrophilicity comes
45 with a drawback as GO membranes swell gradually with increasing humidity and rapidly when
46 immersed in liquid water. The swelling compromises the selectivity of the membrane as d
47 increases gradually up to 1.0 nm in a humid environment[21] and up to 1.3 nm when immersed
48 in liquid water.[6] At this large d , the selectivity of GO membranes is compromised because
49 large ions can permeate through the membrane together with water molecules[9]. In some
50 experimental studies, the swelling of GO membrane has been reported to a much larger d (~6
51 nm)[22] although in a recent review it was mentioned that this was likely to be due to partial
52 delamination of the membrane.[23] As well as a reduction in selectivity, swelling of GO
53 membranes to a very large d may also lead to their mechanical instabilities (i.e. complete
54 delamination). Thus, knowledge and control of the swelling mechanism in GO membranes is
55 key to optimising their performance for aqueous separation processes.

56 The phenomenon of swelling and shrinking of porous materials, including GO membranes, is
57 the result of the balance of attractive and repulsive forces between surface of the membrane
58 and the strength of adsorbent-adsorbate interactions. In the case of GO membranes, the
59 attractive van der Waals (vdW) and repulsive electrostatic interactions between the GO layers
60 is influenced by the surface chemistry that is controlled by the amount and type of oxygenated
61 functional groups on the surface of the GO flake and their possible ionisation in the presence

62 of water. Experimental evidence shows that the swelling of GO membranes to $d = 1.0$ nm near
63 the saturated vapour pressure is associated with adsorption of 50% to 60% of their weight in
64 water.[20,21] The gradual increase in adsorption at low humidity and the final adsorption
65 capacity at saturation varies between membranes depending on their surface chemistry which
66 determines the membrane hydrophilicity and the size of d at various humidity conditions.
67 Experiments and computer simulation studies have shown that varying the surface chemistry
68 alters the adsorption properties. For example, it has been shown that a high concentration of
69 functional groups could increase size of d [24] and the water adsorption capacity at low partial
70 pressure.[25,26] However, the important effects of ionisation of functional groups on GO
71 membrane swelling is not well established.

72 The subtle interplay between humidity, functional group ionisation and swelling of GO
73 membranes is difficult to monitor and control experimentally and is often neglected in
74 molecular simulation studies. A study by Mouhat *et al.* on a single flake of GO using Ab Initio
75 Molecular Dynamics (AIMD) shows that the epoxide and hydroxyl groups on the surface of
76 GO flakes partially ionise in the presence of water.[27] Hydroxyl ionisation, which occurs due
77 to the lower pK_a of the functional groups compared to the pH of solution,[28] leaves a net
78 negative charge on the surface of the flake. On the contrary, epoxide ionisation does not lead
79 to a net surface charge as the partial charges are distributed within the oxygen and carbon atom
80 of the epoxide groups. This AIMD simulation result suggests that computer simulation studies
81 should incorporate ionisation of functional groups to be able to capture realistic properties of
82 GO membrane. Since GO membranes are produced from an assembly of individual GO flakes,
83 the surface chemistry and ionisation state of the functional groups may determine their
84 mechanical stability and selectivity. The surface chemistry of GO membrane reported in
85 literature is however wide and difficult to rationalise because of the wide variety of oxidation
86 pathways taken to fabricate the membrane. For instance, there is large variability observed for
87 membranes prepared using Brodie's and Hummer's method.[1,23,29–31] A deeper
88 understanding of how the surface chemistry of GO membranes affect the swelling properties
89 and the water adsorption mechanism, can be exploited to tune the size of d by altering the
90 oxidation pathway to control the amount of functional groups available on the surface of GO
91 flake or by heat treatment to reduce the oxidised area on the flake.[32]

92 In this work the role of ionised functional groups on water adsorption at various humidity
93 conditions and the induced swelling of GO membrane in liquid water was investigated using

94 molecular simulations. Specifically, the Grand Canonical Monte Carlo (GCMC) and Molecular
95 Dynamics (MD) techniques were employed in combination with atomistic models of GO
96 membranes that consider the ionisation of hydroxyl functional groups on the surface of GO
97 flakes. The role of ionised functional groups on the adsorption of water are analysed using the
98 adsorption curve of GO membrane over a range of chemical potential values and surface charge
99 densities. Finally, the internal pressure in z -direction, P_{zz} , which is normal to the plane of GO
100 membrane, was also calculated in this study to understand the effect of the surface charge on
101 the swelling of GO membrane in bulk liquid water.

102 **2.0 METHODOLOGY**

103 The coordinates of an atomistic 4.17 nm x 4.25 nm graphene sheet, periodic in x and y
104 dimensions, were generated using Visual Molecular Dynamics (VMD).[33] To generate the GO
105 flake model, the basal plane of graphene sheet was subsequently randomly decorated with
106 hydroxyl and epoxide functional groups. Although the lateral dimensions of the modelled GO
107 sheets are much smaller than the real material ($10^2 - 10^3$ nm) due to computational cost
108 limitations, periodic boundary conditions were applied in all three dimensions to represent a
109 section of the bulk material. The functionalisation step is carried out using the in-house code
110 reported in Williams *et al.*[34] The oxygen to carbon ratio was set to 1:3, based on experimental
111 data.[2,3,5,35] The ratio between hydroxyl and epoxide group is reported experimentally to be
112 1:1 by Lee *et al.*[21] In this work a ratio of 1.5:1 was used to ensure that there was enough
113 hydroxyl groups to vary the extent of ionisation over a wide range. This results in an average
114 hydroxyl surface density of 8 OH/nm². The functionalised GO flake was energy minimised to
115 allow it to bend and create wrinkles because of an increase/reduction in surface tension from
116 functionalisation. Four independently functionalised and energy minimised flakes were then
117 stacked on top of each other to form a GO membrane model as shown in **Figure 1** with a
118 predefined interlayer spacing, d , defined as the approximate interlayer spacing measured
119 between centre of mass of carbon atoms from the nearest layer. The d was varied between 0.7
120 to 1.3 nm with an interval of 0.1 nm. The range of d was chosen to reflect the experimental
121 interlayer spacings for a variety of humidity values ranging from the completely dry state to a
122 fully hydrated GO membrane immersed in liquid water, respectively.[16,20,21]

123

124 **Figure 1:** Initial configuration of a dry GO membrane model used in this study shown for
 125 interlayer spacing of 1.0 nm. a) uncharged membrane (NGO) without any counter ions, b)
 126 charged (3QGO) membrane with counter ions. Blue: sodium ion, purple: oxygen atom of
 127 epoxide group, green: oxygen atom of hydroxyl group, white: hydrogen atom of hydroxyl
 128 group, black: graphene backbone (carbon atom)

129 The first GO membrane model has zero surface charge, i.e. none of the hydroxyl groups were
 130 deprotonated. This model represents a neutral membrane which is typical of those used in
 131 computer simulation studies of GO membranes.[22,36–39] GO membrane models with three
 132 different surface charge densities were also built to study the effect of surface charge on the
 133 adsorption of water in GO membrane. In the charged membrane models, randomly selected
 134 hydroxyl functional groups on both sides of the GO flake surface were deprotonated to create
 135 a net negative charge. Ionisation of epoxide groups was not considered in this study because it
 136 does not lead to any net surface charge on the GO flake.[27] The surface charge density, σ_{GO} ,
 137 of a single GO flake is calculated using **Equation 1**;

$$138 \quad \sigma_{GO} = \frac{n_q \cdot q_e}{2 \cdot A_{GO}} \quad (1)$$

139 where n_q is the number of ionised hydroxyl groups, q_e is the charge of electron
 140 (-1.60×10^{-19} C) and A_{GO} is the surface area of one side of GO flake. The surface charge of
 141 each flake is then used to calculate the average surface charge density of the GO membrane. A
 142 σ_{GO} , of -63 mC/m² and -120 mC/m² were obtained by deprotonating 10% and 20% of the

143 hydroxyl groups, respectively. These values fall within the experimental data range (between
 144 -120 and -10 mC/m²).[5,28,40,41] In addition, an arbitrarily higher surface charge density of
 145 -176 mC/m², obtained by deprotonating 32% of the hydroxyl groups was chosen for
 146 comparison purposes. The specific value of 32% for deprotonation of hydroxyl groups is used
 147 to produce an even number of ionisations equally distributed on both sides of each GO flake.
 148 The three surface charge densities (10%, 20% and 32%) will be referred to as 1QGO, 2QGO
 149 and 3QGO throughout.

150 To maintain electroneutrality in the charged models, the necessary number of monovalent
 151 counter ions, N_{Na+} , were inserted randomly into the interlayer space of the charged membrane.
 152 In our simulations, we used the TIP3P-EW model to simulate water molecules,[42] the
 153 parameters from Joung and Cheatham to model counter ions[43] and the CHARMM potential
 154 to model the GO membrane.[44] **Table 1** summarises the values of surface charge of all GO
 155 membrane models used in this study and the number of counter ions required to neutralise the
 156 simulation box.

157 **Table 1:** Value of surface charge for each GO membrane model and the number of counter
 158 ions required to neutralise the simulation box.

Hydroxyl deprotonation (%)	Name of GO membrane model	σ_{GO} (mC/m ²)	N_{Na+}
0	NGO	0	0
10	1QGO	-63.29	56
20	2QGO	-119.80	106
32	3QGO	-176.31	156

159
 160 The adsorption of water in GO membranes was studied using Grand Canonical Monte Carlo
 161 (GCMC) simulations, in which the chemical potential, μ , temperature, T , and volume, V , are
 162 kept constant. Due to the nature of this simulation ensemble, the dynamics of water permeating
 163 the basal plane of GO membrane from the edges is not included in this study. During the
 164 simulations, the Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential is shifted and truncated at 1.2 nm and the cross-
 165 species LJ parameters calculated using Lorentz-Berthelot mixing rules. The Coulombic long-
 166 range interactions are calculated using the Ewald summation with real space cut-off at 1.2 nm.
 167 The GO membrane model was held rigid during the simulation. Three types of Monte Carlo

168 (MC) moves were considered in the GCMC adsorption simulation. The first two MC moves,
 169 centre of mass translation and rotation, are applied to both water molecules and counter ions
 170 with probability of 0.25 for each move. The third move is the insertion/deletion MC move with
 171 probability of 0.5 that is exclusively applied to water molecules to simulate adsorption. The
 172 higher probability was given to the insertion/deletion move to improve computational
 173 efficiency. The number of equilibration steps employed varies depending on the value of σ_{GO}
 174 and d , but in general this is never lower than 1.25×10^6 steps. Production runs were carried out
 175 over 2×10^7 steps for the uncharged GO membrane and 2×10^8 for the charged GO membranes.
 176 To investigate the gradual filling of the interlayer space, the GCMC adsorption simulations
 177 were carried out at various chemical potential values, up to that corresponding to bulk liquid
 178 water, μ_l . μ_l was obtained from a separate GCMC simulation of liquid water by iterating the
 179 chemical potential to give the correct bulk density of 997 kg/m^3 at 300 K. The chemical
 180 potential value calculated from GCMC is a contribution of the ideal and excess part ($\mu_l =$
 181 $\mu_{ideal} + \mu_{excess}$). The ideal part could be estimated with, $\mu_{ideal} = -k_B T \cdot \ln \left[\frac{(V/N_l)}{\Lambda_l^3} \right]$, where
 182 k_B is the Boltzmann's constant, V is the volume of the simulation box, N_l and Λ_l is the number
 183 and thermal de Broglie wavelength of water molecule. Using this iteration approach, a value
 184 of $\mu_{excess} = -26.15 \text{ kJ/mol}$ for bulk liquid TIP3P-EW water model at 300 K and 1 bar was
 185 obtained, which is within the range of value reported in literature for the original bulk liquid
 186 TIP3P water model[45–49] and the total value of μ_l obtained was -45.40 kJ/mol . The chemical
 187 potentials used to study water adsorption was varied in the range between -45.40 kJ/mol and
 188 -151.32 kJ/mol (**Table S1**). The lower bound corresponds to the lowest value of the chemical
 189 potential at which water adsorption was observed.

190 In order to establish whether the GO membrane would swell when immersed in bulk water, the
 191 final GCMC configuration of each model is used to calculate the pressure acting normal to the
 192 GO flake layering, P_{ZZ} . The calculation of the pressure during a GCMC simulation is a
 193 relatively expensive task, thus the calculation of P_{ZZ} was performed using MD simulations
 194 carried out in the canonical ensemble (NVT) with the GROMACS software version
 195 2018.4.[50] P_{ZZ} was calculated using **Equation 2**, where V is the volume of the system, E_{kin} is
 196 kinetic energy and \bar{E}_{ZZ} is the virial in the z -direction.

$$197 \quad P_{ZZ} = \frac{2}{V} (E_{kin} - \bar{E}_{ZZ}) \quad (2)$$

198 A 1 ns simulation was used to calculate P_{zz} with a time step of 1 fs. The value of P_{zz} was
199 sampled every 1 ps and the first 200 ps equilibration data were omitted from the calculation.
200 The uncertainty in P_{zz} was calculated using block averaging with block sizes of 100 ps. The
201 exact same simulation parameters used in the adsorption GCMC simulation are used in the MD
202 simulation. The temperature of 300 K was controlled using the Nosé-Hoover thermostat[51,52]
203 using a relaxation time of 1 ps. As no constraints on the coordinates of GO atoms were used
204 during the MD simulations, the interlayer distance d imposed in the GCMC simulations may
205 slightly deviate during the MD simulation as the membrane structure relaxes towards its local
206 energy minimum. In the real experiments, whether the hydrogen ions released upon
207 deprotonation of the hydroxyl groups remain within the membrane interlayer space or migrate
208 outside is not known. Thus, MD simulations were performed to calculate P_{zz} considering two
209 separate situations *i*) Na^+ counter ions are kept within the simulation cell and *ii*) Na^+ counter
210 ions are removed, and a background charge was used to maintain electroneutrality of the system
211 instead.

212 3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

213 Examples of GO membrane configurations during the adsorption process are shown in **Figure**
214 **2**. For each value of the chemical potential and for each GO membrane model, the amount of
215 water adsorbed, M , is calculated in terms of weight percentage (wt%) of water uptake per unit
216 weight of adsorbent, as shown in **Equation 3**, where m_w is the molar mass of water (18.02
217 g/mol) and m_{GO} is the molar mass of membrane (**Table S2**).

$$218 \quad M \text{ (wt\%)} = \frac{m_w}{m_{GO}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

219 To observe the adsorption process, the amount of water adsorbed, M , is plotted against the
220 value of chemical potential in **Figure 3**. Generally, water uptake is negligible at very low
221 chemical potential values and increases sharply as the chemical potential approaches the bulk
222 liquid value. In the charged membrane models, an initially gradual increase in water content is
223 followed by rapid channel filling at high chemical potentials while in the uncharged membranes
224 only an abrupt increase in adsorbed water is observed irrespectively to the value of d .

225

226 **Figure 2:** Representative snapshots of the 1QGO membrane model with interlayer spacing of
 227 1.0 nm for chemical potentials of a) -113.49 kJ/mol, b) -75.66 kJ/mol, c) -56.75 kJ/mol, d) $-$
 228 45.40 kJ/mol. In blue: sodium ion, purple: oxygen atom of epoxide group, green: oxygen atom
 229 of hydroxyl group, white: hydrogen atom of hydroxyl group, black: carbon atom, iceblue: water
 230 molecules.

232

233 **Figure 3:** Amount of water adsorbed, M , for a) NGO, b) 1QGO, c) 2QGO, d) 3QGO membrane
 234 as a function of chemical potential, μ . The dashed vertical line shows the chemical potential of
 235 bulk liquid water for the TIP3P-EW water model at 300 K and 1 bar, $\mu_l = -45.40$ kJ/mol and
 236 the onset of adsorption at -65 kJ/mol for the uncharged membrane and at -113 kJ/mol for the
 237 charged membranes.

238 **Figure 3** shows that the value of μ at which water starts to be adsorbed in the membrane is
 239 different between the uncharged and charged membranes. In the charged membrane models,
 240 the onset of adsorption occurs at a lower chemical potential value of -113 kJ/mol compared to
 241 the uncharged membranes where water starts to be adsorbed at chemical potential value of -65
 242 kJ/mol. Since the chemical potential is related to pressure, this corresponds to uptake of water
 243 at a lower partial pressure. This observation shows that the charged membranes are more
 244 hydrophilic compared to the uncharged one due to the presence of the deprotonated hydroxyl

245 groups which are favourable adsorption sites for the water molecules. To identify the
 246 adsorption sites, the radial distribution function, $g(r)$, calculated between water molecules, ions
 247 and the functional groups is calculated using **Equation 4**;

$$248 \quad g(r) = \frac{1}{\langle \rho_B \rangle_{local}} \frac{1}{N_A} \left\langle \sum_{i \in A}^{N_A} \sum_{j \in B}^{N_B} \frac{\delta(r_{ij} - r)}{4\pi r^2} \right\rangle \quad (4)$$

249 Where A is the reference atom type, B is the selected atom type, $\langle \rho_B \rangle_{local}$ is the atom density
 250 of type B atoms averaged over all spheres around atom A, N_A is the number of atom A, N_B is
 251 the number of atom B, r_{ij} is the distance between atom A and B, r is the maximum radius to
 252 calculate for atom pairs and angular brackets indicate the ensemble average.

253 The $g(r)$ shown in **Figure 4** confirms that the deprotonated hydroxyl groups are the most
 254 favourable sites for adsorption at low chemical potential (corresponding to the onset of
 255 adsorption) in the charged membranes. The strong interaction between water molecules with
 256 ionised functional groups on GO flake is also observed in the computational study by Qiao *et*
 257 *al.*[11] In both charged and uncharged membranes, no significant peaks are observed between
 258 the water molecules and the other, non-ionised, functional groups (hydroxyl and epoxide),
 259 however, a very intense peak is observed between the hydrogen of water and the oxygen of a
 260 deprotonated hydroxyl group at $r = 0.16$ nm in the charged membranes. The position of this
 261 peak is within the range of the geometrical definition of hydrogen bond[53] suggesting that
 262 hydrogen bonds might be formed between the deprotonated hydroxyl groups and water
 263 molecules. The $g(r)$ calculated between the oxygen atom of water molecules and the Na^+
 264 counterions also shows a strong peak at 0.25 nm. Since the counterions and the deprotonated
 265 hydroxyl groups are in close proximity (0.24 nm) (**Figure S3**), they could be assumed to be a
 266 single adsorption site.

267

268 **Figure 4:** Radial distribution function, $g(r)$, between hydrogen atoms of water molecule (HW)
 269 and oxygen atom of functional groups on the surface of GO membrane and between oxygen
 270 atoms of water molecule (OW) and the counterions (Na^+) calculated for a) 1QGO b) 2QGO c)
 271 3QGO d) NGO at onset of adsorption. Deprotonated hydroxyl group, O^- (blue square),
 272 hydroxyl group, OH (red circle), epoxide group, OE (green triangle), sodium ion, Na^+ (purple
 273 triangle).

274 At low loading, the isosteric heat of adsorption, q_{st} , indicates the strength of adsorption between
 275 adsorbent and adsorbate. A more hydrophilic membrane with favourable sites for adsorption
 276 will have a higher isosteric heat value, indicating a stronger interaction between water
 277 molecules and the adsorption site. The isosteric heat is calculated using the ensemble
 278 fluctuation approach which is suitable for non-zero loads[54] using **Equation 5:**

279

$$q_{st} = -\frac{\langle EN \rangle - \langle E \rangle \langle N \rangle}{\langle N^2 \rangle - \langle N \rangle \langle N \rangle} + RT \quad (5)$$

280 where E is the total configurational energy of the system, N is the total number of adsorbed
 281 water molecules, R is the gas constant, T is temperature of the system (300 K), and the angular
 282 brackets denote ensemble averages. **Figure 5** shows the change in isosteric heat as a function
 283 of interlayer distance, d , for the charged and uncharged membranes at the onset of adsorption.
 284 The plot shows that at low loading, the value of q_{st} for the charged membrane is approximately
 285 double that of the uncharged ones. Since the most favourable sites for adsorption are the
 286 deprotonated hydroxyl groups, the value of q_{st} calculated for the charged membranes is mostly
 287 due to the strong interactions between these and the water molecules while in the uncharged
 288 membranes only weaker water/protonated functional groups interactions contribute to the value
 289 of q_{st} . The strength of adsorption on deprotonated hydroxyl groups makes the membrane more
 290 hydrophilic and able to adsorb water molecules at a lower chemical potential compared to
 291 uncharged membrane that does not have strong adsorption sites.

292

293 **Figure 5:** Isosteric heat of adsorption (q_{st}) of water in GO membranes at low load (onset of
 294 adsorption). Black diamond: NGO, blue square: 1QGO, red circle: 2QGO, green triangle:
 295 3QGO.

296 These results clearly indicate that the presence of deprotonated hydroxyl groups on the GO
297 flake has a very strong influence in the adsorption at low chemical potential values (i.e. low
298 partial pressure). At these values of μ (between -91 kJ/mol and -57 kJ/mol depending on the
299 membrane model) the amount of water molecules adsorbed scales linearly with surface charge
300 density due to the increasing number of deprotonated hydroxyl groups. In this region of the
301 adsorption curve the amount of water adsorbed is independent of the interlayer spacing (**Figure**
302 **3**) since adsorption occurs only in the proximity of the deprotonated groups. An exception was
303 observed in 3QGO membrane (**Figure 3d**) for interlayer spacing of 0.7 nm which has a lower
304 water adsorbed at low chemical potential region. This can be attributed the high number of
305 counterions within the membrane channel that reduces the relative free pore volume for water
306 to be adsorbed.

307 As the chemical potential increases, the amount of water adsorbed gradually increases until all
308 the adsorption sites (i.e. the deprotonated hydroxyl groups) are saturated. At chemical potential
309 higher than approximately -57 kJ/mol, the water content increases rapidly for charged and
310 uncharged membranes and is no longer directly proportional to the number of deprotonated
311 hydroxyl groups on the flake. As the chemical potential approaches the bulk liquid value, the
312 water content is dominated by the value of d which determines the approximate number of
313 water layers that can be accommodated in the interlayer space (**Figure 3**). **Figure S1** shows
314 that for $\mu = \mu_l$, water approximately forms a monolayer for $d = 0.7$ nm to 0.9 nm, a bilayer for
315 $d = 1.0$ to 1.2 nm and a trilayer for $d = 1.3$ nm. At the bulk liquid chemical potential, μ_l , the
316 amount of water adsorbed is proportional to the size of interlayer spacing as shown in **Figure**
317 **6**. It is interesting to observe that even at μ_l , membranes with higher surface charge have higher
318 water content, despite the increase in volume that is occupied by counterions. This is justified
319 considering that the density of a salt solution increases with concentration[55,56] due to the
320 compact arrangement of the water molecules in ion hydration shell.

321

322 **Figure 6:** Amount of water adsorbed, M (wt%) in all GO membrane models at bulk liquid
 323 chemical potential (μ_l). Black diamond: NGO, blue square: 1QGO, red circle: 2QGO, green
 324 triangle: 3QGO. Error bars are smaller than the size of the symbol.

325 To understand whether the higher number of waters adsorbed at μ_l is a direct consequence of
 326 the surface charge, we look at the change in the total potential energy, U_{total} , for water-water
 327 and GO-water interactions as the chemical potential approaches the bulk liquid water value. In
 328 this calculation U_{total} is normalized by the amount of adsorbed water molecules and calculated
 329 using **Equation 6**;

$$330 \quad U_{total} = \frac{U_{LJ}^{SR} + U_{Coulomb}^{SR}}{N_w} \quad (6)$$

331 where U_{LJ}^{SR} is the short-range Lennard-Jones potential, $U_{Coulomb}^{SR}$ is the short-range Coulomb
 332 potential and N_w is the number of water molecules adsorbed. For each membrane model U_{total}
 333 is shown in **Figure 7**.

334 As the chemical potential increases, the magnitude of U_{total} for water-water increases while the
335 magnitude of U_{total} for GO-water interactions decreases. This phenomenon is due to the
336 increasing number of water molecules within the membrane channel which gradually saturate
337 the most favourable sites for adsorption. Once all the favourable sites have been saturated, the
338 adsorbed water molecules act as a “nucleation site” for new water molecules to be adsorbed.
339 **Figure 7a** shows that, at high chemical potential, adsorption is dominated by the water-water
340 interaction in the uncharged membrane. This is accompanied by a crossover of U_{total} for GO-
341 water and water-water interactions as the chemical potential increases. In the charged
342 membranes, the potential energy crossover is only observed for the least charged membrane
343 model 1QGO (**Figure 7b**). For the 2QGO and 3QGO (**Figure 7c** and **7d**) membranes, the
344 water-water U_{total} continues to become more negative with increasing chemical potential while
345 the GO-water U_{total} becomes less negative, but a crossover of potential is not observed. This is
346 due to the high count of favourable adsorption sites on the surface of membrane but also to the
347 high number of counterions in the pores that together with the water act as additional adsorption
348 sites.

350

351 **Figure 7:** Total potential energy for water-water (blue circles) and GO-water (red squares),
 352 normalised by the number of adsorbed water molecules at increasing chemical potential for a)
 353 NGO, b) 1QGO, c) 2QGO, d) 3QGO. The black arrows indicate where the potential energy
 354 crossover occurs (i.e the water-water energy dominates over the GO-water energy).

355 In order to assess the effect of the surface charge on the swelling of GO membranes when
 356 immersed in water, the pressure normal to the GO flake layering, P_{ZZ} , was calculated for all
 357 GO membrane models using bulk liquid water chemical potential, μ_l . The sign and magnitude
 358 of the pressure may result from two contributions: one due to the electrostatic repulsion and
 359 van der Waals (vdW) attraction between individual GO sheets in the membrane and one due to
 360 the solvation pressure arising from the adsorbed water intercalated within the membrane
 361 channels. A negative P_{ZZ} indicates that the membrane interlayer distance would contract/shrink
 362 as there is insufficient repulsive forces (surface charge and solvation pressure) while a positive
 363 P_{ZZ} suggests that the membrane would expand/swell. The equilibrium d occurs for models with

364 P_{zz} close to zero indicating that at that interlayer spacing, the membrane is at mechanical
 365 equilibrium with the external pressure and the membrane would neither shrink nor swell. The
 366 values of P_{zz} for each membrane model at μ_l are shown in **Figure 8**. In the neutral membrane,
 367 where there is no net surface charge, the normal pressure within the membrane is always
 368 negative, as there is no strong repulsion between the sheets. The pressure contribution of P_{zz} in
 369 the uncharged membrane is primarily due to the solvation pressure from intercalating water
 370 within the membrane channel and the vdW attraction between the membrane layers. This result
 371 shows that an uncharged membrane would not swell even when immersed in liquid water. This
 372 contradicts the experimental observations and suggests that the uncharged model is not
 373 appropriate for studying the swelling of GO membranes.

374
 375 **Figure 8:** Internal pressure within membrane in z -direction (P_{zz}) at bulk liquid chemical
 376 potential (μ_l) for a) NGO, b) 1QGO, c) 2QGO, d) 3QGO. Blue squares: with counter ions, red
 377 open squares: without counter ions.

378 Two MD simulation setups were used to calculate P_{ZZ} in the charged GO membrane: one with
379 counterions within the channels and another with the counterions removed. In general, the
380 calculation with counterions shows a lower pressure value compared to without counterions.
381 The presence of explicit counterions within the membrane screens the repulsion between GO
382 layers more effectively, thus reducing the repulsive contribution due to surface charges. In all
383 charged membrane models with $d = 0.7$ nm, a very high positive pressure was observed. This
384 suggests this value of d is not stable when surface charges are included and the membrane
385 should swell, in agreement with experimental reports.[6,16] In contrast, the neutral membrane
386 shows a negative P_{ZZ} at 0.7 nm but also for any other values of interlayer distance. This result
387 suggests that the presence of deprotonated functional groups on the GO surface are necessary
388 to observe swelling in GO membrane. At $d = 0.8$ nm, P_{ZZ} drops significantly before starting to
389 fluctuate. The drop in pressure at 0.8 nm becomes less significant with increasing surface
390 charge density, again showing the significant impact of surface charge on the swelling of GO
391 membranes.

392 In the charged membrane, P_{ZZ} fluctuates with respect to d . To understand these fluctuations of
393 P_{ZZ} , the structure of water within the membrane channel was analysed. At $d = 0.7$ nm, a sharp
394 peak in the density profile indicates the formation of a water monolayer, leading to a high
395 positive value of P_{ZZ} . As the interlayer spacing increases to 0.8 nm and 0.9 nm, the free pore
396 volume increases but a complete bilayer cannot yet be accommodated, resulting in loosely
397 packed water molecules, and broadening of the density profile (**Figure S1a** and **S1b**). The
398 formation of approximate monolayer, bilayer and triple layer structures are observed in
399 membrane with $d = 0.7$ nm, 1.0 nm and 1.3 nm, respectively. For other d values in between
400 these interlayer distances, the channel size does not allow an integer number of water layers,
401 which again means loosely packed water molecules, thus reducing the solvation pressure
402 contribution within the channel. This pressure fluctuation is in qualitative agreement with the
403 simulations of Ulberg *et al.* and Striolo *et al.* on confined water within pristine graphene
404 nanopores.[57,58] However, although the contribution of the solvation pressure on the swelling
405 of GO membranes is quite significant, it is not enough to be the major cause of GO membrane
406 swelling. For example, in the 1QGO model P_{ZZ} is always negative for $d > 0.7$ nm, even when
407 d is commensurate with an integer number of water layers. The value of the surface charge on
408 the other hand strongly affects the swelling of GO membrane. As the surface charge increases,
409 the P_{ZZ} becomes more positive irrespectively whether the counterions are included or not in the
410 calculations. It is also worth noticing that this effect may be reduced in the experimental

411 samples which are characterized by a higher disordered pore structure compared to the model
412 employed here, which assumes a fairly well-defined 2D pore geometry. Having said that, the
413 value of the internal pressure calculated for the charged model with intermediate charge
414 (2QGO) predicts an internal pressure value which is in reasonable agreement with that measure
415 by Talyzin *et al.* of 220 bar for a μm thick GO membrane.[59]

416 The repulsive Coulombic energy between GO flakes in NGO, 1QGO, 2QGO and 3QGO
417 increases with the number of ionised hydroxyl groups on the GO surface, which is 0.27, 0.69,
418 1.89 and 2.55 kJ/mol/nm² respectively. When the surface charge is very high, the membrane
419 should swell to a larger d as the repulsion between GO layers is high, compromising the
420 mechanical stability of the membrane. These results agree with the work of Gudarzi *et al.* who
421 demonstrated that GO flakes with a high surface charge value remain dispersed in aqueous
422 solution due to electrostatic repulsion.[41] The value of P_{zz} calculated also suggest that the
423 interlayer spacing in the 2QGO and 3QGO models would swell beyond 1.3 nm, due to the
424 strong repulsion from the ionised hydroxyl groups at μ_l . This result provides insight into the
425 effect of surface charge on the swelling of GO membranes and shows that deprotonation of
426 functional groups, resulting in a net charge on the GO sheets, is the major factor explaining the
427 swelling.

428 In addition to the electrostatic screening, the presence of explicit counterions could lead to
429 cross-linking between deprotonated functional groups that bind opposite GO layers. This effect
430 is likely to be more significant in membranes with a small d and a high density of counter ions.
431 It can be observed for the 3QGO membrane model with 0.7 nm interlayer spacing, for which
432 the internal pressure changes drastically when counter ions within the membrane are present
433 (**Figure 8d**). The pressure difference is too large to be attributed to the only electrostatic
434 screening effect. This linker effect has previously been reported in the experiments and
435 simulations of Chen *et al.*[60] in which hydrated sodium ions were shown to bind to adjacent
436 GO sheets in the membrane, forming a stable hydrogen bond network and resisting the swelling
437 of membrane. Moreover, a study by Sivaniah *et al.* shows that incorporating positively charged
438 nanodiamonds in between GO membrane layers could overcome humidity-induced swelling of
439 the membrane.[61] To understand if the difference in pressure calculated from our simulation
440 is due to cross-linking for 3QGO / $d = 0.7$ nm, the $g(r)$ and its integral (**Figure S3**) between
441 sodium ions and deprotonated hydroxyl groups is calculated. In addition, the density profile of
442 charged hydroxyl groups and sodium ions across the simulation cell is calculated (**Figure S4**).

443 The coordination number of deprotonated hydroxyl groups around sodium ions is always less
444 than 1 except for the 3QGO membrane model with $d=0.7$ nm which has a coordination number
445 of 1.4. Combined with the density profile shown in **Figure S4**, this suggests a partial sodium
446 ion cross-linking effect between the opposite GO layers within the membrane. Since the fate
447 of the counterions in the real experiment is not known, the value of P_{zz} calculated with and
448 without counterions can be considered as the theoretical lower and upper limits to the real
449 pressure, where ions may either migrate from the membrane or remain within the membrane
450 channel.

451 **4.0 CONCLUSIONS**

452 In this study we have investigated the effect of surface charge on the water adsorption
453 properties and swelling of GO membranes. At low chemical potential (at the onset of water
454 adsorption), the ionised functional groups are the most favourable sites for adsorption. These
455 are energetically favourable sites for water adsorption compared to other functional groups due
456 to the formation of strong hydrogen bonding. The presence of ionised functional groups in the
457 charged GO membranes shifted the adsorption onset to a lower chemical potential value as the
458 membrane is getting more hydrophilic. The effect of the surface charge on the swelling of the
459 membrane was investigated by calculating the internal pressure, P_{zz} . GO membranes with a
460 higher surface charge have a more positive pressure, while uncharged GO membranes have a
461 negative pressure, regardless of the interlayer distance. This indicates that the uncharged
462 membrane would never swell due to the weak electrostatic repulsion between the sheets.
463 Increasing the surface charge increases the value of P_{zz} indicating that the surface charge is
464 mainly responsible for the swelling of GO membrane in the presence of water and that there is
465 an upper limit (which for ordered membrane as those modelled here is around -120 mC/m²)
466 above which the membrane delaminates. Interestingly the simulations show that the presence
467 of counterions in the channels has a double effect: at low chemical potential they reduce the
468 swelling (screening the flake/flake electrostatic repulsion) but at high chemical potential
469 increase the amount of water adsorbed. Our results clearly indicate that the surface charge
470 could be used to tune the interlayer spacing of hydrated GO membranes. This could be achieved
471 by altering the oxidation method, which is known to result in different types and quantities of
472 functional groups, or the pH of the solutions which would affect the degree of oxidation of
473 surface groups.

474 Finally, our work demonstrate that the charged GO membrane model is a more realistic
475 representation of GO membrane to be used in computer simulation as suggested by Mouhat *et*
476 *al.*[27] The charged model produces better qualitative predictions for hydration and swelling
477 data of GO membranes than the uncharged model. This finding highlights the need for the
478 application of new simulation methodologies such as sorption-relaxation cycle (SRC)[62–67]
479 that can simultaneously account for the complex interplay between water adsorption,
480 membrane swelling with a more realistic GO membrane model that include surface ionisation.

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488 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

489 **ORCID**

490 Mohd Rafie Bin Shaharudin: 0000-0002-1962-9090

491 Christopher D Williams: 0000-0002-5073-5924

492 Paola Carbone: 0000-0001-9927-8376

493 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

494 The authors have no competing financial interests.

495 **MATERIALS AND CORRESPONDENCE**

496 Supporting information including figures and data tables.

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